

Kaharingan

also known as “Dayak Hinduism”, “Agama Kaharingan”, “Kepercayaan Kaharingan”, “Hindu Kaharingan”

By William Noseworthy, Cornell University

Entry tags: Hinduism, Southeast Asian Hinduism, Religious Group, Syncretic Religions, Animist, Southeast Asian Religions, Reform Movement

Kaharingan is the modern and contemporary name of the Dayak traditional religion that is most clearly understood as a form of Dayak particularist Hinduism. During various points in recent history, this group was subsumed under the classifications of Agama Hindu by the Indonesian state. However, there are substantive differences between the Dayak forms of Hinduism and Hinduism elsewhere in the archipelago that can be explained as a feature of Dayak history, as well as through the ideas of a single figure: Tjilik Riwut.

Date Range: 1945 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Central Kalimantan

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Indonesia, Borneo

Central Kalimantan is an Indonesian province. It was created in 1957, out of a division of South Kalimantan, in an effort to give Dayak people greater sovereignty. Palangkaraya, the capital, was created in a three year construction project. The population of Central Kalimantan is only a plural majority Dayak, however (46%), with Javanese (22%) also making up a significant minority of the population. Islam is the majority religion (about 75% of the population), yet it is also this region that the small Kaharingan community considers home.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kaharingan, panaturan, tampanan taluh handiai : buku ajaran agama. Author: Majelis Besar Alim Ulama Kaharingan Indonesia. Publisher: Huang Nyelu: Majelis Besar Alim Ulama Kaharingan Indonesia, 1973.
- Source 2: Panaturan. Author: Majelis Besar Alam Ulama Kaharingan Indonesia. Publisher: [Palangka Raya]: [Majelis Besar Alim Ulama Kaharingan Indonesia], 2001.
- Source 3: Panaturan. Author: Sekolah Tinggi Agama Hindu Negeri Tampung Penyang. Publisher: Palangka Raya: Sekolah Tinggi Agama Hindu Negeri Tampung Penyang, 2005.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/x83526>

– Source 1 Description: Dayak Materials at the British Museum. Art Objects pertaining to Iban Dayak in Malaysia are not relevant to this entry per se, beyond being part of the broader Dayak cultural sphere. However, those pertaining to Kalimantan and the Ngaju Dayak are especially relevant, as are those pertaining to the Ma'anyan or Ma'anjan.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/Panaturan/page/n3/mode/2up>

– Source 1 Description: This is an, online, open-access version of the "panaturan" based on the 1985/2004 revisions of the text, revised again for 2015.

Notes: There are scant relevant online primary texts for this group, other than the Panaturan. Other than this version, available on Archive.org, there are no other widely accessible primary sources for the study of this group as of this writing. However, some blogs and other informal sources may exist.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there has been historical violent conflict. There is evidence to suggest that Dayak members of the Indonesian military, including those under Tjilik Riwut's command participated in the genocide in Indonesia from 1965 - 1966. There was also violent conflict between different Dayak groups at various points in history, both prior to, and through the colonial period, as well as Dayak confrontations with Dutch colonial officers that potentially turned violent; and Dayak conflicts with Javanese, Banjarese, or other groups, including Indonesian Chinese.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Some of the more violent episodes of Dayak history (early colonial period; and Indonesian Genocide) were so widespread across the archipelago that it is difficult to ascertain whether the aforementioned patterns of violence involved Dayak off the island of Borneo. That said, they certainly involved Dayak violence in other parts of Kalimantan, including South Kalimantan.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Tjilik Riwut himself is a famous example of a "re-convert" from Christianity to Dayak "traditional religion" or "Animism."

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Marriage ritual could convert Ngaju Dayak from one religion (Christianity, Islam, Kaharingan) to another. Typically, Islam has the strongest gravitational pull historically in marriage relations, however.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Attempts to recruit members to "return" to the "traditional Dayak religion" occurred especially during the life of Tjilik Riwut.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:
– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:
– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:
– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:
– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:
– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
– No

Notes: Tjilik Riwut was a governor of Central Kalimantan. The institutional support the province received was filtered in a few cases into support for Kaharingan institutions during his time as governor. Additionally, the networks with Java were maintained as a form of support.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– No

Notes: Tjilik Riwut was a governor of Central Kalimantan. The institutional support the province received was filtered in a few cases into support for Kaharingan institutions during his time as governor. Additionally, the networks with Java were maintained as a form of support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
– No

Notes: Tjilik Riwut was a governor of Central Kalimantan. The institutional support the province received was filtered in a few cases into support for Kaharingan institutions during his time as governor. Additionally, the networks with Java were maintained as a form of support.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: Tjilik Riwut was a governor of Central Kalimantan. The institutional support the province received was filtered in a few cases into support for Kaharingan institutions during his time as governor. Additionally, the networks with Java were maintained as a form of support.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Tjilik Riwut was a governor of Central Kalimantan. The institutional support the province received was filtered in a few cases into support for Kaharingan institutions during his time as governor, which is a form of preferential economic treatment. Additionally, the networks with Java were maintained as a form of support.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that apostates (i.e.: converts to Christianity and Islam) are also quite common and there is not a universal sense that apostates are to be punished, or even that they necessarily will be, in all historical and anthropological accounts.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: There is a sense in that individuals who convert to Christianity or Islam might be "abandoning ancestors" and thus receive social shunning as a result of that.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– No

Notes: There is a sense in that individuals who convert to Christianity or Islam might be "abandoning ancestors" and thus receive a form of divine retribution for this action.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 160000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 5.9

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: In the existing historical and anthropological literature, the general consensus is that the formal scripture of the panaturan was created by a formal organization of Dayak priests, in a process that took place from the 1970s through the 1990s.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: So long as we interpret the Dayak traditional long-house as a form of communal house, but with central ritual functions that go beyond the every-day use of the structure, these are monumental religious architecture. There does not seem to be as much literature emphasizing the nature of these structures in comparison to, say, Batak examples. That said, there is evidence from Lee (1962) suggesting that similar structures were also historically present in British Borneo; i.e.: among related Dayak groups outside this particular religious community and outside the sample region. However, there are also spirit houses (sandung) that are associated with the interment of remains as another form of religious architecture, although they are also not monumental. Finally, in more modern constructions there are "worship halls" (balai basarah) that more closely resemble common conceptions of a temple.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 50

Notes: Historically, nearly 100% percent of constructions were longhouses. This is not the case today. Modern constructions began to become much more prominent across Borneo from the 1980s onward.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 50000

Notes: Assuming 100 meters by 500 meters, which would be enormous.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: Height for longhouses is typically measured from their height off of the ground to the base floor. The ceiling height is not typically recorded in field records.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This data is not well recorded enough to make an assessment.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This data is not well recorded enough in anthropological accounts to make an assessment.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 50

Notes: This would presume that open space, smaller individual structures, and funerary space are all part of the settlement, while agricultural space are presumed outside the settlement. The percentage would be smaller from the 1980s onward, with the increase of space devoted

to non-longhouse living and agriculture, as well as the incursion of plantations.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes

↳ Temples:
– Yes

Notes: Balai basarah are "worship halls" that may well appear to essentially be temples to outside observers.

↳ Altars:
– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:
– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
– On persons
– At home
– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The Tree of Life

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Much of the iconography blends these images together with the use of artistic motifs that are not explicitly abstract symbols, yet are a recognizable sign of Dayak artistic culture.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Heaven

Notes: Although there are various forms of the Dayak Kaharingan cosmology, it is important to note that there was an intentional effort to conflate the cosmology with Muslim and Christian cosmologies resulting in more direct assertions of spaces like "Heaven" and "Hell."

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

|

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: There are materials that more explicitly refer to a concept of "karma" among the Kaharingan Dayak during the 21st century. The concept does not appear to pre-date 1945 from other records and likely emerges through a need to appeal to conceptions of Hinduism established by the Indonesian state.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Post-cremation remains are interred during a secondary burial and a funerary feast (Tiwah)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: Cannibalism was historically practiced among Dayak populations, as was head-hunting. However, these practices were virtually eliminated by the end of the 19th century, as was the practice of human sacrifice at Tiwah funerary feasts.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: In effect, this occurs pre-cremation.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: This is especially important and notable.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: However, in the historical past, human co-sacrifices were present.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Not in every instance and there may be a great range. However, during the Tiwah feasts, large numbers of water buffalo and also pigs are sacrificed and fed to the community.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Although not always in all circumstances.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Rare.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Although not always in all circumstances.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: There are both primary cemeteries and secondary burials which are not precisely cemeteries but rather ossuaries placed at the center of ritual spirit-house constructions.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Within Dayak contexts, the supreme high-god is often "the great hornbill." Kaharingan refined this concept with the naming "Ranying Hatalla Langit." In this construction "Langit" means "sky." Tingang is a common name for "the Great Hornbill" among non-Kaharingan Dayak, although sometimes the two are conflated. Other names for "sky god" or "high god" might include the epithet "King of the Sun" (Raja Tontong Matanandau) and "King of the Moon" (Kandarohan Tambing Kabanteran Bulan). Others still might include "Mahatara" - who is probably derived from Sanskrit contexts, "Tara" meaning "Earth - via the Javanese court of Majapahit; or "Bhatara Guru" a common Island Southeast Asia epithet of "Shiva" who is associated with both Batak and Balinese contexts as well. The name "Ranying Mahatara Langit" may include some Islamic influence via the name "Allah" OR other variations such as "Hatala," or "Lahatala."

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Although the high god is not chthonic, within Dayak cosmology the underworld is associated with a female water-serpent. She is sometimes portrayed as the "sister" of the upper-world/sky-world "Mahatala." She is most often called "Jata" although she is also known as a "Naga." The term "jata" does imply some connection with "origins" although this naga is also called "Tambon" a Dayak word for "Water-snake."

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: However, in the historical past, there were stronger links between notions of "gods" and "elites" that can be found in the records of the "Maharaja Buno" and "Maharaja Sangiang," especially as "sangiang" are helper spirits, not necessarily human - often non-human in form.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Over time, the description of the high god was increasingly similar to Muslim and Christian descriptions of Allah and God, respectively.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge of saints and spirits.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: There is some evidence to suggest that these notions have decreased over time in favor of a greater emphasis on a high god as "all loving."

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Historically, this is more the case. However, over time, the spirits and other gods that were additionally worship were conflated with "angel and saint" categories, so that they became subordinate to the high god and technically only worship of the high god is permissible, while other supernatural figures are more simply venerated.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: However, there is communication through religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Also through ritual specialists, although this is not the only means of communication.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: There are especially "sangiang" - which are atmospheric deities or helper-spirits.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Not always, but it is possible.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They watch over health, wealth, well-being, and death.

Notes: These divinities include Sahor, Bapa Sangumang, Indu Sangumang, and Tempon Telon.

– Yes

Notes: There are especially "sangiang" - which are atmospheric deities or helper-spirits.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They have been conflated into a subordinate status in order to adhere to the ideals of a monotheistic system in more recent decades.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There are especially "sangiang" - which are atmospheric deities or helper-spirits.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Yes, pantheon was consolidated intentionally into a monotheistic framework with the high god as the only god and the others being regulated to the status of saints, spirits, and angels.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Typically these are described as part of Dayak “traditional customs” or “customary law,” although ethical codes might be an alternative translation for “adat.”

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Orthopraxy

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In the past, human cosacrifice as part of tiwah rituals was viewed as positive.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Coming of age rituals remain important.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Not always, however. There is a question about degree and severity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: The degree to which this has been the case seems to have varied from period to period.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Adherence to adat.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Although those practitioners who more strictly attempt to adhere to monotheism may have expressed this idea, it does not seem to be popular in historical and anthropological records.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Natural forces. Force of nature itself.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

Notes: However, strict monotheists may attempt to adhere to this vision in some records.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: However, strict monotheists may have contended - and may still contend - that only the high god has the power to do this.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists and elite members more strongly emphasize rewards in the afterlife, although popular practitioners also participate.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Fortune bestowed upon descendants.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: There is not a strong emphasis on prophets or messianic beliefs. However, there may be some attempts to adhere to notions of prophets and messianic visions in some interpretations of the Kaharingan religion in an attempt to make the religion more closely match expectations of Christianity and Islam.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: These norms are described as part of Dayak adat.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: More so for specialists.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: However, tattooing is popular across Dayak groups.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: However, there was ritual suicide in the past, as well as ritual cannibalism.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Food and animal sacrifices to be consumed.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: However, marginalization has sometimes occurred.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These are not necessarily daily rituals. They might be life-cycle rituals or they might be calendrical, as well as daily in a handful of households.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: 50 - 100 depending on the size of the temple, most likely.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: These are calendrical rituals.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: In popular rituals, yes. In more formal rituals, the evidence seems to be mixed. In Tiwah funerary feasts: absolutely.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:
– Yes

↳ Dress:
– Yes

↳ Ornaments:
– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other:
– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: It is notable that in the case of Dayak communities, there is no strong record of formal varna-like distinctions that one might find, say, on the island of Bali (with the Balinese triwangsa). Instead,

Dayak seem to bifurcate more simply into "elite/non-elite" status, although distinctions are fluid in the historical record. There is indication that the Dayak practiced enslavement in the historical past, prior to the early 20th century. However, perhaps with the elimination of enslavement during the Dutch era, class distinctions flattened over the course of the 20th century.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Although Tjilik Riwut's military troops operated as such during his lifetime.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: However, during the life of Tjilik Riwut, they were integrated into the formal military of Indonesia.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Contemporary Dayak is romanized.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Although not a written language per se, there have been previous hypotheses about "high and low" Dayak languages. However, counter positions also suggest that these were merely distinctions between root and borrowed terms. See: Dyen (1956).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is significant that the group had to formalize their calendar to gain recognition from the Indonesian government. The formalization of the calendar resulted in the raising of the ritual of Bawi Ayah to a "high holiday" - in part made possible by the decline of "Tiwah" funerary feasts over the course of the Dutch era. "Bawi Ayah" is probably most similar to the Island Southeast Asian rice-goddess "Dewi Sri," who remains prominent on Java and Bali.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)

- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: H.G. Wales Quaritch. *The Cosmological Aspect of Indonesian Religion*.

Reference: Olivier Sevin. *Les Dayak du centre Kalimantan : étude géographique du pays ngaju, de la Seruyan à la Kahayan*. Paris: Éditions de l'Office de la recherche scientifique et technique outre-mer.

Reference: Martin Ramstedt. *Politics of Taxonomy in Postcolonial Indonesia*. *Historical Social Research / Historische Sozialforschung*, 44(3)

Reference: Anne Schiller. *An "Old" Religion in "New Order" Indonesia: Notes on Ethnicity and Religious Affiliation*. *Sociology of Religion*, 57(4) doi: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3711895>.

Reference: Anne Schiller. *Talking Heads: Capturing Dayak Deathways on Film*. *American Ethnologist*, 28(1)

Reference: Anne Schiller. *Activism and Identities in an East Kalimantan Dayak Organization*. *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 66(1)

Reference: Taufiq Tanasaldy. *New Order and Dayak marginalization (1966-1998)*. (Taufiq Tanasaldy), *Regime Change and Ethnic Politics in Indonesia*. Brill.

Reference: Martin Baier. *The Development of the Hindu Kaharingan Religion: A New Dayak Religion in Central Kalimantan*. *Anthropos*, 102(2)

Reference: Isidore Dyen. *The Ngaju-Dayak 'Old Speech Stratum'*. *Language*, 32(1) doi: <https://doi.org/10.2307/410657>.

Reference: Y Lee L. *Long House and Dayak Settlements in Borneo*. *Ekistics*, 14(84)